
NARA Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype

TR-10-04
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Renaissance Computing Institute

NARA Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype

Reagan W. Moore

Arcot Rajasekar

Antoine de Torcy

Mike Conway

Jewel Ward

Jon Crabtree

Mason Chua

University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill

Wayne Schroeder

Michael Wan

Sheau-Yen Chen

University of California, San Diego

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1. Introduction:

The Data Intensive Cyber Environments (DICE) Group is collaborating with the National Archives and Records Administration on the development and demonstration of fundamental concepts required for implementing preservation environment infrastructure. Specifically, policy-based data management systems are being applied in the Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype (TPAP) to investigate preservation at scale in a distributed environment. The lessons learned in the implementation are used to evaluate whether the fundamental preservation concepts are adequate, or whether they need to be revised to manage unforeseen requirements. A simple way to characterize the success of this approach is whether the preservation environment is based upon sufficiently generic infrastructure that it can enforce any desired preservation policy, including new preservation policies that manage new types of record formats.

The NARA TPAP project has developed a characterization of preservation environments that builds upon multiple levels of abstraction. Each level of abstraction is used to implement a required preservation concept. The choice of abstraction levels is intended to implement the capabilities necessary for:

1. **Infrastructure independence.** The properties of the preservation environment should be sustainable independently of the choice of storage and database technology. This implies that the preservation environment should build upon a highly extensible architecture, capable of interacting with any choice of technology.
2. **Communication with the future.** The preservation environment should provide representation information for each record (provenance, descriptive metadata, data structure) that is adequate for interpreting the meaning of the record. Representation information for the preservation environment (policies, procedures, state information) is also needed to characterize how the preservation environment is being managed. An implication is that the system needs the ability to migrate preservation procedures onto new technology. Communication with the future implies not only use of future technology, but also migration of past policies and procedures onto the future technology.
3. **Assessment of communication from the past.** For a future archivist to make assertions about the properties maintained by a preservation environment, he or she will need to know how the records were managed. This implies the need to track application of all versions of preservation policies over time, in order to validate preservation properties in the presence of evolving requirements. The future archivist needs a detailed description of the representation information for the preservation environment and audit trails of all operations that were performed.
4. **Validation of assessment criteria.** A preservation environment is built from commodity components that are subject to multiple types of failure modes: media failure, in which files lose their integrity; hardware failure, in which disk heads crash and tape robots

smash tape cartridges; software failure, in which software systems execute previously undetected bad code instructions under heavy load; operational failure, in which operators execute obsolete procedures that overwrite and lose data; natural disasters, in which fire or earthquake destroy entire archives; malicious users, in which vulnerabilities in the operating systems are exploited to overwrite data. A preservation environment can only make assertions about the last time that the assessment criteria were validated. The validations must be re-verified as frequently as the archivist requires for assertions about the integrity of the preservation environment to remain viable. A validation of assessment criteria is a single point in time verification.

5. **Persistent objects.** It is not sufficient to be able to incorporate new technology. The representation information for the preservation environment contains policies and procedures that define the desired management plan. The management plan must be ported to each new version of the preservation environment. In this view, the records are maintained in their original format. The procedures that parse the records are written using infrastructure independent representations of I/O commands, making it possible to port the procedures to new technology (operating systems). Since the original procedure can continue to parse and display the record, the dominant concern of format obsolescence is avoided. To enable use by new access methods, versions of the records will need to be created that are migrated to the formats needed by the more sophisticated display applications of the future. Thus the preservation environment needs the ability to apply original procedures as well as future procedures to each record. This in turn may require the management of multiple versions of each record: the original format, and new encoding formats required by new display mechanisms.
6. **Preservation as an active process.** At the point in time when new technology becomes available, both the old and new technologies are present. If preservation is viewed as an active process, then incorporation of new technology is reduced to an interoperability problem. The new technology is integrated into the preservation environment using the mechanisms that enable infrastructure independence. Policies can then be established for migrating records from the old technology to the new technology. For this approach to be successful, the archivist must continually seek to incorporate new technology. This has the advantage that new technology is typically cheaper, higher performing, and more sophisticated than old technology. An active preservation process keeps a preservation environment relevant by supporting access by the most recent display mechanisms.

The TPAP approach is based on the use of data grid technology to manage records that can be distributed across multiple types of storage systems and across multiple institutions. The data grid ensures that the properties of the preservation environment are correctly maintained, that the required preservation processes are applied, and that validation of the trustworthiness of the preservation environment can be demonstrated.

The concepts behind policy-based preservation environments were presented at a demonstration of the TPAP testbed at the 2010 SAA Research Forum in Washington DC on August 10, 2010 and at a meeting of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO)/International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Joint Technical Committee 1 (JTC 1) study group on Digital

Content Management and Protection (DCMP) in Shenzhen, China on August 23, 2010. Informal live demonstrations of the TPAP testbed were also presented to participants at the Society of American Archivists and to DCMP committee members. The fundamental concepts presented at both conferences are listed in Section 2.

A demonstration of the TPAP testbed was given at the 2010 SAA Research Forum in Washington DC on August 10, 2010. The presentation demonstrated a very simple “dropbox” style interface for ingesting records, the automated application of preservation policies, and the tracking of the status of records as they are being processed. The records were ingested into the TPAP testbed through an interface that ran at the SAA Research Forum meeting site in Washington DC, with records stored on storage resources at the Renaissance Computing Institute in North Carolina. Example preservation processes that were applied included the monitoring of the ingestion of records into a staging area, the detection of viruses, the replication of records, the setting of a retention period, and the verification of integrity information. Two different interfaces were demonstrated: the “Arch” web client provided a simple way to associate policies with a record series; the “iDrop” interface provided a simple way to drag and drop records into a record series and manage their transmission into the preservation environment. Each record series could have a different set of preservation policies, which would be automatically enforced by the preservation environment. A description of the demonstration is provided in Section 3.

The third activity has been a continued analysis of the scalability and performance of the TPAP testbed. For each activity, the person working on the task within the TPAP testbed is identified. The current status of the TPAP testbed is listed in Section 4. A summary of the status of the deliverables of the TPAP testbed is included in Section 5. Section 6 describes the extant research issues, and the investigation of each research issue that was performed within the TPAP testbed. Presentations and papers are listed in Section 7, and a conclusion is provided in Section 8.

2. Preservation Fundamental Concepts

The traditional view of preservation environments is based on the idea that it is sufficient to track all operations that have been performed upon records. Each operation is encapsulated as an event that can be characterized and logged. For each event, metadata that describes the processing and the outcome are created and stored for each record. This approach has several implications:

- The events tell the archivist what he or she did in the past, but do not tell the archivist what should be done in the future.
- If the preservation policies change over time, there is no information available to understand why they changed, or whether they may change again.

The event information is augmented with representation information for each record that is used to assert provenance, original arrangement, and authenticity. The event logs are used for assertions about integrity, chain of custody, and trustworthiness.

Based on the experiences within the TPAP testbed, a preferred approach is policy-driven instead of event-driven. The policies define which preservation procedures should be applied, control the execution of the preservation procedures, and record state information about the outcome of

each procedure. This approach makes it possible to characterize all preservation policies, manage versions of both policies and procedures, and track the evolution of the preservation environment. This is essential if a preservation environment is going to be based on a dynamic process that continually incorporates new technology to avoid obsolescence. With each new set of technology, the associated preservation policies and procedures may also need to be upgraded to implement new preservation guidelines for new data types. This implies that preservation policies and procedures must be versioned, information about which version was used must be recorded, and multiple versions of policies will need to be migrated into the future. In turn this implies that an infrastructure independent form of preservation procedures is required to be able to manage the continued migration of prior procedures to new technology. With each new set of policies and procedures, the assertions that can be made about the preservation environment will need to be verified. The ultimate goal is the ability to validate that the preservation environment is working correctly and maintains the required preservation properties after each technology upgrade.

A challenge that has only been partially addressed within the TPAP testbed has been the development of an understanding of the required preservation procedures. The TPAP testbed has implemented 219 basic operations related to data management, but a much wider range of operations may be needed to handle the wide variety of data types that require preservation. An approach at quantifying the procedures needed for parsing data formats builds upon the following data abstraction levels:

- Data structures are imposed upon bits to create bytes; words; strings; and arrays.
- The data structures are named in order to assign information content through semantic labels.
- The semantic labels are organized into a vocabulary with associated standard units.
- Relationships are imposed upon the structures to define knowledge. Unfortunately, each type of relationships currently requires a different set of procedures for the associated operations:
 - Logical relationships imply operations on semantic vocabularies through ontologies.
 - Spatial relationships imply operations on structures that are mapped onto coordinate systems and onto geometries.
 - Functional relationships imply transformations on variables stored within records.
 - Procedural relationships imply time ordering of processes into workflows.
 - Epistemological relationships imply evaluation of systemic properties through application of assessment criteria.

A viable preservation environment provides procedures that implement the operations needed for manipulating each of the above types of relationships. Fortunately, the TPAP testbed has implemented a generic procedure-based environment that can be used to apply all of the above types of operations. Each operation is encapsulated as a functional unit (called a micro-service) that can be chained together with other operations to implement the desired preservation process. Through use of infrastructure independence, the micro-services can be ported to new technology as it becomes available, ensuring the ability of the preservation environment to apply all previous preservation procedures.

For this approach to be feasible, the preservation environment should be characterized through the following preservation abstraction levels:

- *Purpose* - reason a preservation environment is assembled. This defines the types of records that will be preserved, the types of operations that will be performed upon the records, and the preservation policies that will be enforced. A rough categorization of the purpose can be made that is based on: preservation of diplomatic records that are maintained forever; preservation of records that have a well-defined retention schedule and a specified original arrangement; preservation of records for which original arrangement is not kept (as in a digital library); and preservation of records that will be re-used and re-purposed by new user communities, requiring the application of new user interfaces. These purposes require different preservation properties, policies, and procedures.
- *Properties* - attributes needed to ensure the **purpose**. This defines the state information that is needed to track the preservation environment attributes. Note that state information is needed not only about the records (representation information), but also about how the preservation environment is managed. The TPAP testbed manages 205 preservation attributes.
- *Policies* - controls for enforcing desired **properties**. This defines when procedures are applied, the workflows associated with each procedure, and the administrative tasks that are needed to manage the records. It is not sufficient to apply policies only on ingestion and access. Policies are needed to govern all administrative tasks as well. This implies the need for policy enforcement points within the preservation environment that are much more extensive than simple ingest and access. The TPAP testbed manages 71 policy enforcement points.
- *Procedures* - functions that implement the **policies**. The TPAP testbed chains basic functions (micro-services) together to implement workflows that are applied at the remote storage location under the control of a policy that is executed as rule within a distributed rule engine. An implication is that basic functions require the interchange of structured information for successful chaining. The TPAP testbed manages the exchange of structured information through standard structures in memory. For operations that are executed on multiple storage locations, the in-memory structures are serialized and sent over the network to the remote location where they are unpacked and reconstituted as in-memory structures. This approach ensures that the workflows will work the same, whether they are executed entirely within a single storage platform or across multiple storage platforms. The TPAP testbed manages 229 micro-services.
- *State information* - results of applying the **procedures**. The TPAP testbed manages 205 state information attributes that span information about users, records, collections, storage systems, and rules. The attributes include information about quotas, the load on the system, outstanding or deferred operations, audit trails, and rule versions.
- *Assessment criteria* - validation that **state information** conforms to the desired **purpose**. The assessment criteria can be evaluated through periodic rules that verify a well-defined property. This evaluation must directly address the issue of scale, as preservation environments will contain petabytes of data and hundreds of millions of files. The TPAP testbed has demonstrated the development of deadline schedulers that evaluate an assessment criterium at the slowest possible rate to meet a required deadline. This

ensures that the processing is completed with minimal impact on active use of the preservation environment.

- *Federation* - controlled sharing of **logical name spaces**. Given the wide range of failure modes, long-term preservation requires replication across independently managed preservation environments. If one environment fails for whatever reason, an independently managed environment is needed to ensure preservation of the records. The independent environment can be managed as a deep archive, in which records are pulled into the preservation environment, deletion is disabled, and all updates are managed as versions of records. In effect, a write once environment is needed that is capable of tracking all updates on the original environment, while preserving the ability to present any version of any records. The TPAP testbed supports federation across data grids, enabling the demonstration of deep archives.

These are the essential elements for policy-based data preservation. The demonstrations at NARA and the SAA Research Forum implemented these capabilities. The ISO/IEC JTC 1 DCMP meeting had an additional focus on preservation environment interoperability. In the purest form, interoperability is implemented through the ability to execute the other preservation systems' protocols. A simple example is based on the export of records from one preservation environment and the ingestion of the records into a new preservation environment, while being able to:

- export records packaged with all preservation metadata
- ingest records and interpret preservation metadata
- assert the original preservation policies are still enforced
- apply the same preservation procedures as in the original preservation environment
- verify that the same preservation properties have been maintained

This process actually occurs each time a preservation environment is modified to use new technology. Thus the same generic framework that supports evolution of the preservation environment should also support interoperability between preservation environments. For the TPAP testbed, this has effectively been demonstrated through the migration from the original SRB-based TPAP testbed to the iRODS-based TPAP testbed.

3. TPAP Demonstrations at NARA

Each of the above concepts was demonstrated at NARA through the Arch and iDrop interfaces to the TPAP testbed. The significant components of the demonstration were:

- Ease of use of the interfaces. The complexity of applying policies and procedures can be quite daunting to non-computer science majors. The Arch interface was designed to present policies to the user in terms of natural language constructs. The user entered the minimal amount of information needed to establish the policy input parameters. The user then defined which policies would be applied to a record series. The actual implementation of the policy on a record series was managed by the interface as attributes defined for each record series collection. Finally, only the information about the associated policy was presented with the record series to avoid any confusion over what was being done.

- Automation of data transfers. A major challenge is the transmission of the records from their original site into the preservation environment. The iDrop interface manages the transmission of data from the remote computer into the data grid. This required extending the abilities of the client to monitor the success of the transmission, maintain a log of all attempted data transfers, track error reports for all problems that were observed, and present a list to the user of what was accomplished. Given experience with the failure modes, the interface can be extended to automate recovery from standard errors. This greatly decreases the effort needed to ingest large numbers of records.
- Implementation of infrastructure independence. The records are referenced through a logical name space. The mapping to the actual file location is managed as a policy within the iRODS data grid. From the user's perspective, the data grid does all of the work that is needed to decide where to put the data, interact with the remote storage location, monitor the integrity of the data, and manage system metadata. Since the simplest possible user interface was demonstrated, this meant that some preservation policies had to be implemented by the data grid administrator, and applied as an additional level of policy control beyond that specified on the record series. An example is the choice of physical file name to use for each logical record. This can be implemented as a standard naming convention for the preservation environment by the data grid administrator, and applied independently of the choice of number of replicas that was made by the record series administrator. The ability to apply multiple sets of policies was facilitated by the multiple points of policy enforcement that are trapped by the TPAP testbed.
- Integration with externally provided technology. The TPAP testbed is highly extensible. This capability was demonstrated through the use of an external virus detection program that was invoked through a remote execution command. The policy defined by the record series administrator invoked a virus scan program that could have been acquired from any reputable vendor. The program was integrated into the policy workflow automatically, and the results generated by the program were tracked and added as metadata onto each record that was tested. The ability to integrate external executables into a workflow is an essential extensibility mechanism required by any preservation environment.
- Distributed environment. The choice of storage location was controlled by the TPAP testbed across the multiple resources that were available for storing data. The storage resources were distributed between the East and West Coasts of the United States. A preservation environment should span multiple institutions that are geographically separated.
- Authenticated access. The TPAP testbed authenticates each user and validates the authorization of each operation. The range of authentication mechanisms includes challenge-response, Kerberos, Grid Security Infrastructure, and Shibboleth.
- Extensible metadata environment. The policy input parameters that were associated with each record series were stored as metadata on the collection. Each collection could have a different set of preservation policies, a different set of policy input parameters, and different descriptive metadata. This extensibility is necessary to enable the environment to evolve and manage new policies over time and to support new record series.
- Automated policy detection. A generic policy for processing the ingestion of records was developed. The generic policy queried the collection under which the record was being saved, extracted the set of policy input parameters from the collection attributes, decided

which rule needed to be executed, and automatically invoked the correct procedures. The implication is that the invocation of policies was reified in terms of the policy input parameters. This minimizes the number of rules that need to be implemented, and characterizes each policy in terms of the input parameters. This provides a succinct way to describe preservation policies that can be exported for interpretation by future archivists.

- Standard policy sets. A policy repository was created within the TPAP testbed to hold an XML-based characterization of each policy. The process decoupled the specification of a policy from the association of the policy with a record series. Thus a policy could be defined, and then be independently applied to multiple record series, each with a different set of input parameters.
- Standard rule sets. Each policy was composed from multiple rules that in turn were managed within a rule repository. Each rule was characterized as an ASCII file and stored in a rule repository within the TPAP testbed. Thus new rules could be added and new versions of rules could be created.

The actual demonstrations for the Society of American Archivists were restricted to 10 minutes in duration, to allow as many archivists as possible to see the technology. This greatly reduced the amount of information that could be conveyed. For the NARA demonstration, a full hour was spent on descriptions of the technology and demonstrations of the simplified user interfaces.

4. TPAP Preservation Environment

Within the TPAP preservation environment, multiple activities have demonstrated the application of the above concepts. Each activity illustrates the type of active management process that needs to be applied within a viable preservation environment

4.1 Migration to new technology

The TPAP testbed has been upgraded to the latest version of the iRODS data grid software (version 2.4). This was needed to improve scalability of the testbed (through additional indices on the iCAT catalog), fix memory leaks, fix bugs observed in federation of data grids, correct instability problems observed with the Reliable Blast UDP protocol, and improve the ability to bulk load 50 files at a time into the TPAP testbed.

4.2 Development of new interfaces

The development of the Arch and iDrop interfaces was controlled by explicit requirements from the TPAP testbed for usability and automation of data transfers. The development of the interfaces was tightly integrated with the development of a repository for standard rules, a repository for standard policies, and a generic rule invocation mechanism based on a characterization of policies by their input parameters.

A scalability test with the iDrop interface was conducted on the TPAP testbed. An external small RAID system was identified with 300,000 files organized in a directory hierarchy. The top-level directory was dragged into the iDrop interface to initiate transfer of all 300,000 files to iRODS. The files were ortho-photos of the state of North Carolina with average size about 200 kBytes. The transfers ran to completion in about 4 hours, for an average transfer rate of 4.1 MBs/sec and an average file ingestion rate of 20 files per second. The transfer rate was limited by the speed of the external RAID system. The test was done in parallel with other tasks that

were using the RAID system. The successful completion of the transfers was very encouraging, and a test with a one million-file transfer will be done next.

A more limited test was done at NARA, with approximately 1000 files. This test was meant to verify that the iDrop application could be loaded at NARA with one click via Java WebStart, and that iDrop could successfully connect and transfer data to NARA iRODS servers. Further tests are also being planned at NARA in addition to a planned 1,000,000 file ingestion test at RENC. Before further tests proceed, additional instrumentation will be added to iDrop to display transfer rates and a progress bar.

4.3 Testing of TPAP for scalability and performance

The scalability of the TPAP testbed was examined by testing the data grid software on higher performing systems that had a much larger number of hardware threads (32 instead of 2). The tests demonstrated that a much higher ingestion rate could be achieved than has been measured on the TPAP testbed. The tests included use of both traditional disk and Solid State Storage devices. The hardware configuration was:

- All processes (iCAT, iRODS server and client) run on a single server. This avoids network latency.
- Powerful server - 4 CPUs with 8 hardware threads per CPU
- iCAT runs on SSD disk or SATA disk
- iRODS server runs on SATA disk

The test conditions emulated the current TPAP holdings:

- 10 millions files already in the iCAT
- 3 tests – iput (ingest a file), iget (retrieve a file) and irm (remove a file)
- Each client process performs operations on 10,000 zero-length files. The purpose of the test was to evaluate the rule base and database overheads.

The results are reported for each type of operation:

- 1) iput (upload) – this is the only command that can be run in bulk mode with ingestion of 50 files at a time or in normal mode with ingestion of one file at a time. Two additional options were tried:
 - RAM200 – bulk load 200 files at a time.
 - RAM1000 – bulk load 1000 files at a time.

No. of concurrent processes	Operation	Aggregate Number of Files/sec			RAM	RAM200	RAM1000
		SSD	Disk				
1	normal	175	76				
1	bulk	454	400				
4	bulk	1658	1470				
8	bulk	2892	2330				
10	bulk	3482	-				
12	bulk	3651	2698	4231	4669	4580	
14	bulk	3918	2904				
16	bulk	4009	2862	4738	4984	5333	
20	bulk	1885	1139	2178	2321	2372	

The tests showed that up to 5,000 zero-length files per second could be loaded into the system. This is an ingestion overhead of less than 0.2 milliseconds per file which is much less than the latency of the disk seek time (7 milliseconds).

2) iget (download)

No. of concurrent processes	Operation	Aggregate Number of Files/sec		
		SSD	Disk	RAM
1	normal	125	133	
4	normal	246	253	
8	normal	518	580	
10	normal	1081	1068	
12	normal	1407	1326	1352
16	normal	1366	1350	1410
20	normal	1360	1324	1362
24	normal	872	869	

The retrieval rate was lower by a factor of three since a single file was retrieved with each client request. This is still less than 1 millisecond of overhead latency per file.

3) irm (delete). The expectation was that this rate would be substantially lower as the deletion of files required removal of metadata from the iCAT catalog. In practice, the TPAP testbed moves files into a trash collection to improve the perceived rate.

No. of concurrent processes	Operation	Aggregate Number of Files/sec		
		SSD	Disk	RAM
1	normal	91	49	
4	normal	158	85	
8	normal	302	141	
10	normal	647	295	
12	normal	843	413	
16	normal	1030	503	1082
20	normal	961	574	1203
24	normal	687	568	1030

4) File transfer speed was tested two ways:

- small files – the entire irods source tree with 10,573 files and directories, and 62.4 MB of data was transferred
- one large file - 1 GB, using 16 I/O threads for data transfer

Operation	SSD resource	Disk resource
small file put	176.7 sec	175.5 sec
small file get	66.4 sec	60.0 sec
large file put	553 MB/sec	553 MB/sec
large file get	528 MB/sec	556 MB/sec

Observations:

- The advantage of running the iCAT database on SSD disk is less than expected.
- Overall, the iRODS performance is relatively good. It is important to run the iCAT and the iRODS servers on the best hardware.
- The peak aggregate upload rate is improved by 38% using SSD. The upload rate for a single process in "normal" mode is improved by 130%.
- There is no improvement in the iget (download) rates which means the overhead for querying the iCAT is about the same for the two systems. It took about 0.5 sec to list 10,000 files for both systems.
- The irm (delete) rate is improved by about a factor of 2 using SSD.
- The iput rate is much faster than the iget rate or the irm rate.
- The difference between the iput and the iget rate can be attributed to the bulk mode of the iput. The bulk operation significantly reduces the amount of communication between the client and server.
- But the difference in speed between iput and irm cannot be explained this way because the irm command issues a single API to the server to remove a collection recursively. The difference is most likely due to the relatively long time needed to delete metadata in the iCAT.
- The data transfer performance of the SSD resource is virtually the same as the disk resource.

A specific challenge for the TPAP testbed was the ability to run collection migrations to completion. Attempts to manipulate very large collections had not completed successfully. Multiple steps were taken to evaluate these problems for whether they were related to indices for optimizing the metadata catalog, or whether they were related to memory leaks. In particular, iRODS catalog (ICAT) performance testing procedures were developed and refined and some initial analysis performed. The goal was to create a reliable test environment, on modest hardware, where controlled experimentation can be performed which will aid in the analysis of ICAT changes, with predictive value to larger-scale and higher performing hardware environments. Some progress has been made toward these goals and additional development is planned.

A particular Redhat Linux DICE-UCSD host, srbbrick14 located at UCSD, was utilized for the testing. A current version of iRODS and PostgreSQL was installed (on alternative ports), and various scripts and commands utilized to ingest sets of files and establish user-defined metadata (Attribute Value Unit triplets - AVUs) on them. PostgreSQL dumps of the ICAT database were made in various stages.

Two test suites were found to be useful and one not. One useful test is a modified 'poundtest.sh', which is part of the continuous build/test system and spawns multiple processes to run 'iput' and 'iget' on sets of zero-size, medium, and large files. To be most useful its 'imeta add' and 'imeta qu' operations were removed to have it strictly dealing with file ingestion and access. Another useful test is to use simple 'imeta qu' and 'imeta ls' commands, in a case similar to that of a site that encountered performance problems with iRODS 2.3 which were solved in iRODS 2.4.

The 'irodsctl devtest' test suite was found to be less useful for this. It tests various operations and options, including every preset iCAT SQL form (currently 291 types). Because of that, some of the unusual operations may dominate the execution time. For example, if there are many collections, the renaming of a zone will take a long time, as it needs to update the zone name in each row of the collection table; but this is very rarely done and so optimization should be focused elsewhere.

In the following chart, the iCAT catalog contained 1 million files and either 500,000 AVUs (5 attributes per file on 100,000 files) or 1 million AVUs (5 attributes per file on 200,000 files), and either the iRODS 2.3 indexes or the extended 2.4 indices were in place. Note that the iRODS 2.4 indices contained optimizations necessary for the TPAP testbed.

The AVU search is a 'imeta qu' operation searching for an AVU that either does exist, or does not. The evaluation results are the seconds needed to complete the test.

	PoundTest	AVU Search		AVU List	
		Exist	Not	Exist	Not
500,000 AVUs:					
2.3 Indexes		.44	.26	.07	.07
2.4 Indexes		.09	.06	.07	.07
1 Million AVUs:					
2.3 Indexes	92	.84	.46	.07	.07
2.4 Indexes	98	.07	.07	.07	.07

We conclude that, even at this modest scale, the eventual failure when using only the 2.3 indexes can be predicted, as the performance is decreasing substantially, and linearly, with scale, which would not be the case in a well-tuned DBMS. We also see a slight, but not severe, reduced performance in the Poundtest with the 2.4 indexes due presumably to slight additional overhead in maintaining the additional database indices.

With these procedures and scripts, meaningful and reproducible tests can be performed concerning additional ICAT indices and other changes that might affect performance, accurately determining which future additions will be most beneficial to the TPAP testbed. Also, changes that might improve performance in some situations but reduce it in others, may be detected. The current metadata catalog optimizations have been tested to 200 million files. Further optimization may be needed for catalogs containing a billion files.

5. TPAP Interoperability

The TPAP project has received funding from both NSF and NARA. A major goal has been demonstration of interoperability with preservation technology developed by other projects. Towards this goal, extensions have been made to TPAP to add new preservation capabilities.

5.1 TPAP Integration with Third Party Preservation Systems

The integration of virus detection software was demonstrated as part of the TPAP NARA presentation. This is an example of the remote execution of external code from within a TPAP policy. Discussions have continued with William Underwood of Georgia Tech on the integration

of his file format identification software as iRODS micro-services. When they become available, we will demonstrate their execution on selected NARA digital holdings.

The implementation of legacy format management is a planned future extension. Discussions with the European Union SHAMAN project (Sustaining Heritage Access through Multi-valent ArchiviNg) continue on application of their media service technology for on demand transformation of data formats. The new media services have not yet been distributed by the SHAMAN project, although much of the development has been completed. The format translators are cast as media adaptors and implemented as iRODS micro-services.

5.2 Extensions to TPAP preservation capabilities

A major issue when dealing with massive collections (millions of files) is the management of very long-running processes that require the manipulation of all files in a collection. A deadline scheduler has been written that validates integrity of data collections at the slowest possible rate to meet a deadline. The scheduler and the associated rule engine (with extensions) are based on a re-write of the iRODS rule engine. While the installation on TPAP awaits further testing of the new rule engine, this will enable periodic validation of assessment criteria that require the manipulation of every record. Examples are checksum validation, migration to new data formats, and creation of new archival information package (AIP) containers.

An initial demonstration of the use of AIPs to manage records that contain multiple components has been accomplished through the integration of tar files into TPAP. The associated data grid capabilities included the aggregation of files within a sub-collection into a tar file, the ability to mount a tar file (transparently access the internal files without the user having to unpack the tar file), and the ability to unpack a tar file. These actions are equivalent to the operations needed to manipulate an AIP.

The implementation of micro-services specific to preservation processes developed in the preservation community is an on-going activity. A specific target has been the development of preservation processes to manage social science data sets. A set of 16 policies has been defined that are important to social science. They can be categorized as follows:

- Organization, Environment, and Legal Policies
 1. Define dataset succession plan
 2. Define access policies
 3. Log access for accountability
 4. Reference TRAC (trusted repository audit checklist) criteria
- Community and Usability Policies
 5. Require a deposit agreement
- Process and Procedure Policies
 6. Define iCAT to DDI (database data interchange) discovery crosswalk for descriptive metadata
 7. Store dataset's DDI metadata as object
 8. Define persistent identifiers
 9. Define UNF's (format independent fingerprints) and Checksums
 10. Provide reporting of preservation network
- Technology and Infrastructure Policies

11. Define number of replication copies
12. Define geographic location for the copies
13. Provide authentication policy
14. Provide versioning
15. Provide control for deletion/replacement
16. Define replica validation frequency via UNF's and Checksums

A set of 6 simple rules and 3 sophisticated rules were developed that implemented the top “8” policies. Many of the policies are automatically enforced within the iRODS data grid, such as persistent identifiers, tracking of copy location, and support for deletion and replacement. Rules were written to match the required policy, or adapt an existing rule to match the required policy.

The link to the index page for the iRODS Social Science policies is:

<http://verity.irss.unc.edu/pm/index.php?n=Site.IRODSPolicy>. The URLs for policies that are explicitly enforced by the data grid are left blank in the following list.

A. Organization, Environment, and Legal Policies

1. Defined access policies ::

<http://verity.irss.unc.edu/pm/index.php?n=Site.DefinedAccessPolicies>

2. Log access for accountability :: blank [iRODS provides this functionality.]

B. Process and Procedure Policies

1. Defined persistent identifiers :: blank [iRODS provides this functionality.]

2. Defined UNF's and Checksums ::

<http://verity.irss.unc.edu/pm/index.php?n=Site.DefinedUNFSAndChecksums>

3. Provide reporting of preservation network :: blank [iRODS provides this functionality.]

C. Technology and Infrastructure Policies

1. Defined number of replication copies ::

<http://verity.irss.unc.edu/pm/index.php?n=Site.DefinedNumberOfReplicationCopies>

2. Defined geographic location for the copies ::

<http://verity.irss.unc.edu/pm/index.php?n=Site.DefinedGeographicLocationForTheCopies>

3. Provide authentication policy :: blank [iRODS provides this functionality.]

Additional policies and procedures are under development to improve the capabilities of the preservation environment. They include:

- Implementation of micro-services that mitigate risk of data loss. The specification of the automated replication of records was demonstrated as part of the Arch interface to the TPAP testbed.
- Implementation of testing procedures that verify that the reference implementation can maintain assertions through catastrophes (loss of major components of the system). This is strongly linked to management of versions of policies, and the ability to track which version is currently being applied within the preservation environment. Part of this effort is related to the addition of system metadata attributes to the iCAT catalog to track versions.

- Implementation of a form of federation suitable for preservation environments. Normally policies are used to differentiate between users from multiple data grids. This makes it possible to restrict the operations that a remote data grid user may perform. Thus federation corresponds to the set of procedures that a data grid administrator allows another data grid to execute. This has been augmented with the ability to support soft links of collections across federated data grids and is now available on the TPAP testbed.
- Integration with web services for presentation of records and preservation metadata. The new JARGON stack supports web services as well as other clients. In practice, more than 35 clients can access the TPAP testbed. Specific operations can be exposed as separate web services. For all clients, the actions requested by a user are both authenticated and authorized.

6. Open Research Issues

The iRODS data grid and the rules and procedures developed in the TPAP project are distributed as open source software in an “ERA” module. The entire iRODS software system is available under a BSD open source license from <http://irods.diceresearch.org>. The open research issues have been presented at the ISO/IEC JTC 1 DCMP standards meeting, with the intent of developing a standard vocabulary for describing interoperability, a standard packaging strategy for transforming representation information between different formats, and a standard set of interoperable services for use within preservation environments. Note that the ability to compose standard services by chaining micro-services remains a unique capability of the TPAP preservation environment. Other preservation environments work at the level of discrete services that are not composed from basic functions. Despite this, there is a desire to share services between environments. The goal is to be able to apply the same preservation services on records when they are migrated into another preservation system. Thus both the records and effectively the preservation services can be migrated between preservation environments. The material in Sections 6.1-6.5 and Appendix 4 was presented at the ISO/IEC JTC 1 study group on DCMP.

6.1 *Specification of standard preservation properties*

The properties that a preservation environment should possess are the result of a social consensus formed by the creators of the archive. Properties may be related to preservation of authenticity, or trustworthiness, or original arrangement, or integrity, or completeness, or authoritativeness, or chain of custody. The properties are maintained over time by coding and enforcing policies that govern ingestion of records into the collection, management of the records, and collection access. Each policy controls the execution of procedures that are needed to enforce the desired properties. A procedure may extract required metadata, or replicate a file, or implement a disposition mechanism. After the execution of each procedure, system state information is generated that tracks the results of applying the procedure, such as the metadata values that were extracted, or the location of the replicas, or the list of files for which the disposition policy was enforced. From this perspective, a preservation environment for digital data collections is characterized by the policies that translate to machine-executable procedures, which in turn require maintenance of state information that are self-consistently tracked over the lifetime of the collection.

Interoperability standards can be based on the set of policies and procedures that are needed to ensure preservation properties. Consider the following scenario:

- A record is extracted from an original preservation environment and migrated into a new preservation environment.
- The policies that govern the management of the records are migrated to the new preservation environment
- The procedures that manipulate the records are migrated to the new preservation environment
- The state information that tracks the results of applying the procedures is migrated to the new preservation environment.

An assertion can then be made that the properties of the archive can be maintained across both the original preservation environment and the new preservation environment. This assertion relies on the characterization of the preservation environment as a set of policies, procedures, and state information that can be quantified and moved independently of the choice of implementation technology.

In policy based data management systems, policies are implemented as machine-actionable rules. The rules are composed by linking standard operations into workflows that are applied at remote storage systems. The state information generated by applying the workflows is stored in a metadata catalog that can be queried to verify that the desired properties have been maintained. In particular, a preservation environment is driven by the set of policies and procedures that define properties related to authenticity, original arrangement, integrity, chain of custody, and trustworthiness. Authenticity corresponds to tracking the provenance of the record and asserting the record is the same as the original submission. The original arrangement denotes the order in which records are submitted within a record series. Integrity is managed by testing whether the bits within the record have been corrupted and by using replicas to replace corrupted data. Chain of custody is managed by tracking where the files have been stored. Trustworthiness is validated through assessment criteria developed by standards groups such as ISO MOIMS-rac.

The choice of preservation properties to manage within the preservation environment is normally not quantified by other developers of preservation technology. This remains a major hurdle towards making progress on interoperable preservation infrastructure. Establishing a consensus on all the required preservation properties will be difficult. However, at a minimum the preservation properties consistently include authenticity (provenance information), integrity (mechanisms to verify files are not corrupted), and chain of custody (typically interpreted as an audit trail). More difficult properties to quantify include the ability to display a record in the future through infrastructure independent procedures, and characterization of trustworthiness.

6.2 Specification of standard preservation services

A set of preservation services has been characterized at a high level by the California Digital Library and is listed in Table 1. They correspond to operations

Table 1. High Level Preservation Services

1	Appraisal
2	Accession
3	Logical naming
4	File-based storage
5	Arrangement
6	Description
7	Repository instance
8	Policy configuration
9	Directory typing
10	File differencing
11	Checksums
12	Format typing
13	Containerization
14	Identifier resolver
15	Search

that are performed upon each record during ingestion, and operations that enable discovery of records at a future date. It is possible to consider standard interoperability mechanisms that focus on the ability to apply these services on any preservation environment. Examples of this approach include the development of standards for aggregating files in containers such as Bagit, standard conventions for logical naming of files, and standards for validating integrity (checksum algorithms). While this defines a minimal set of services, it does not quantify the expected behavior of each service. In order to define what a service does, an analysis of each service in terms of basic operations is needed. Within the TPAP testbed, this is accomplished through specification of basic operations as micro-services. This raises the issue that a more appropriate specification of services should be done through chaining of basic functions. This is an aggressive position to take, since few other preservation environments can compose and apply workflows.

6.3 Specification of standard preservation policies

The services listed in Table 1 do not address the administrative tasks that are needed to maintain a preservation environment. The ISO MOIMS-rac assessment criteria for trustworthiness can be expressed as a set of tasks that need to be executed to maintain a viable archive. In effect, a preservation policy is needed for each task to control the frequency at which the task is performed, define the records over which the task is executed, and define the information that must be maintained to demonstrate compliance over time. A standard set of preservation policies can then be constructed that each preservation environment should enforce.

The 52 criteria listed in Appendix 1 are opportunities for development of interoperability standards. Each of the criteria should be implementable as a policy and associated procedures within a preservation environment. By also migrating the appropriate policies, procedures, and state information as records are moved between systems, it will be possible to verify compliance with the original preservation properties.

The task can be simplified by defining generic functions that can be combined to implement the criteria. Twelve of the trustworthiness assessment criteria listed in Appendix 1 reduce to use of a template to define required information content, or to support formatting of information into a desired structure. Eleven of the criteria are enforced through the fundamental framework of a policy-based data management system that supports infrastructure independence. Seven of the criteria are addressed through parsing of audit trails. Six of the criteria are addressed through management of replicas. Three of the criteria are addressed through validation of checksums. The remaining thirteen criteria are implemented as specific procedures that are applied to each record under the control of a rule, such as association of metadata with a record, or the application of a specific process.

If we create generic functions that parse information using a template, or generate a package using a template, we can reduce the effort needed to implement the assessment criteria. Similarly, a generic function can be implemented that parses audit trails for specific information, a generic function can create replicas, and a generic function can validate checksums. We also need a generic function that chooses which preservation policies to implement based on a template that defines policy parameters.

From this perspective, the assessment criteria can be reduced to the application of twenty generic functions within a policy-based preservation framework. This approach is similar to the concept of infrastructure independence that is implemented in data grids. Infrastructure independence is based on virtualization mechanisms for logical naming of files, for interoperability across storage protocols, for interoperability across authentication environments, and for decoupling clients from storage systems through insertion of middleware. The actions of clients are interpreted as a combination of generic operations that are executed on behalf of the client by the data grid. Specifically, policy-based data management systems extend

Table 2. Generic Preservation Functions

1	Parse information from document based on a template
2	Create a document based on structure defined by a template
3	Migrate a document between structures defined by two templates
4	Parse required policies from a template specifying rule parameters
5	Generate audit trails for requested operation
6	Parse audit trails to identify specified event/operation
7	Create replicas
8	Synchronize replicas
9	Create and validate checksums
10	Generate event-based notification
11	Associate required metadata with a record
12	Manage a rule base of preservation policies
13	Apply a required rule to a record
14	Provide unique identifiers for users, records, rules, micro-services
15	Authenticate all users
16	Assign users to roles
17	Authorize all operations based on roles
18	Version policies, micro-services, and state information
19	Manage a staging area for data ingestion
20	Support federation of preservation environments

infrastructure independence to include policy virtualization, the ability to enforce policies on a collection independently of the choice of storage technology and independently of the choice of client. The 20 functions listed in Table 2 are candidates for interoperability standards for preservation functions.

The TPAP testbed provides support for policy virtualization through the installation of a rule engine and rule base at each storage location. The policies for the preservation environment are cast as rules. Each rule is defined for a specific event, governed by a condition, and executed as a workflow composed from basic operations called micro-services. Error recovery is executed through a recovery workflow. All requests for data at the storage system are processed through the rule engine. This ensures that the preservation policies are enforced independently of the choice of access client.

The generic preservation functions for implementing assessment criteria are listed in Table 2. The generic functions are executed within the TPAP testbed infrastructure independence framework that provides the persistent logical name space, access controls, descriptive and provenance metadata support, persistent mapping from the logical name space to the storage location, management of replicas, data transport, and policy execution environment.

6.4 Specification of standard policy enforcement points

Most systems apply policies at the time of ingestion, and create a workflow that supports the validation of content, creation of an Archival Information Package, and storage/replication.

However there are multiple additional places within a data management framework where policies should be enforced. Basically, every operation within a preservation environment should be controlled by an explicit policy. Within the TPAP testbed data grid, policies can be defined at the policy enforcement points listed in Appendix 2. In many cases, the enforcement points correspond to application of policies before an operation is initiated and after an operation is completed.

The question for interoperability standardization is whether these policy enforcement points are sufficient, or whether additional policy enforcement points are needed. This is equivalent to asking whether all of the generic operations that need to be executed by preservation procedures have been trapped with pre- process and post-process policy enforcement points.

Table 3 shows the application of policies as rules when a file is ingested into the data grid. A representative set of rules is shown. A full-fledged archival system will have more processing steps with additional archive-centric and collection-centric procedures. Here we show a minimal set (with many of the operations being null operations) which still give a flavor of the types of workflow that one can easily configure in a production archive system.

In this example, 10 policy points are applied when ingestion occurs. The first three policies are related to authentication and authorization. The second three policies are related to resource management (e.g. choice of resource based on attributes of the ingested object, or quota enforcement) and arrangement. The next two policies are concerned with system metadata extraction and/or assignment. The ninth policy in this list is concerned with the creation of the ingested digital object in the TPAP testbed and concerns all aspects for integrity and provenance (e.g. ownership) maintenance. The tenth policy provides a hook for post-processing of the ingested digital object as required by collection curator and/or the owner of the data object. The Post-process policy can be quite complicated, possibly distributed, and executed after a delay through a scheduling and queuing system. In this example, there are three policies for post-processing but only one is applicable (the other two had guard conditions that were not met by the properties of the digital object; the guard conditions can be based on combinations of type, arrangement, ownership, size, location, etc.). The one post-processing policy that was applied created a replica of the ingested digital object in another physical resource. This policy in turn invoked other policies as part of its execution. The post-processing steps are shown below the line within Table 3.

The example shows that even a simple process such as the ingestion of a file into an archive should invoke explicit policies that govern the desired preservation properties. Each operation performed upon a preservation environment should be controlled by an explicit policy that is migrated with the record. An archivist in the future should be able to verify the policies under which a record was archived.

6.5 Specification of standard micro-services

Within a data grid, micro-services are chained together to implement each of the procedures required by the preservation environment. The number of micro-services can be much larger than the number of assessment criteria. By composing selected standard micro-services into a workflow chain, it becomes possible to implement a required management policy without having to write additional code. The number of micro-services currently supported within the TPAP testbed is on the order of 229. A partial list is shown in Appendix 3.

Micro-services are essential for creating procedures that can be migrated to new operating systems, ensuring that a specific policy can be applied in the future.

Within the TPAP testbed, micro-services invoke a standard I/O library based on Posix I/O. For each storage system, a driver is written that maps from the standard I/O calls to the specific required storage protocol. This means the micro-services are independent of the choice of operating system, and will run equally well on Linux, Windows, or Mac operating systems. Given a standard set of micro-services, it will then be possible to migrate policies with records and ensure that desired preservation properties are maintained no matter which preservation environment is managing a set of records.

The expression of preservation procedures can be quantified by identifying the micro-services from which they are composed. Each micro-service should execute a well-defined standard function, such as file replication, or metadata extraction based on a template, or checksum validation, or query on state information. The standard operations within a preservation environment can then be quantified as standard micro-services. The migration of policies to a

Table 3. Policies Invoked on File Ingestion
ApplyRule: acChkHostAccessControl GotRule: acChkHostAccessControl
ApplyRule: acSetPublicUserPolicy GotRule: acSetPublicUserPolicy
ApplyRule: acAclPolicy GotRule: acAclPolicy
ApplyRule: acSetRescSchemeForCreate GotRule: acSetRescSchemeForCreate execMicroSrvc: msiSetDefaultResc(demoResc,null)
ApplyRule: acRescQuotaPolicy GotRule: acRescQuotaPolicy execMicroSrvc: msiSetRescQuotaPolicy(off)
ApplyRule: acSetVaultPathPolicy GotRule: acSetVaultPathPolicy execMicroSrvc: msiSetGraftPathScheme(no,1)
ApplyRule: acPreProcForModifyDataObjMeta GotRule: acPreProcForModifyDataObjMeta
ApplyRule: acPostProcForModifyDataObjMeta GotRule: acPostProcForModifyDataObjMeta
ApplyRule: acPostProcForCreate GotRule: acPostProcForCreate
ApplyRule: acPostProcForPut GotRule: acPostProcForPut GotRule: acPostProcForPut GotRule: acPostProcForPut execMicroSrvc: msiSysReplDataObj(tgReplResc,null)
<hr/>
ApplyRule: acSetMultiReplPerResc GotRule: acSetMultiReplPerResc
ApplyRule: acSetRescSchemeForCreate GotRule: acSetRescSchemeForCreate execMicroSrvc: msiSetDefaultResc(demoResc,0)
ApplyRule: acPreprocForDataObjOpen GotRule: acPreprocForDataObjOpen
ApplyRule: acSetVaultPathPolicy GotRule: acSetVaultPathPolicy execMicroSrvc: msiSetGraftPathScheme(no,1)

new preservation environment is simplified if the same standard operations are available within the new system.

A preservation environment should be characterized by the policies that are enforced, the procedures that are executed, and the standard operations that are performed. In addition, each procedure generates standard state information, such as the location where the replica was made. It is possible to characterize a preservation environment, and base interoperability between preservation systems on the ability to apply and enforce preservation policies.

Preservation interoperability standards need to include support for preservation policies, preservation procedures, and preservation state information. Preservation policies can include assessment criteria that are periodically executed to verify properties about the preservation environment, such as authenticity, integrity, chain of custody, and trustworthiness. An initial list of the preservation policies and procedures that have been defined for the NARA Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype has been published in previous NARA status reports. The goal is to show that the listed capabilities are sufficient and necessary for the implementation of a preservation environment.

For the ISO/IEC JTC 1 DCMP standards meeting, Ken Thibodeau at NARA provided a list of requirements for preservation environment interoperability, based on a consumer perspective. A listing of the capabilities that have been implemented within the NARA Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype that address these requirements is given in Appendix 4.

7. Presentations and Papers:

One of the objectives behind the NSF funding for the TPAP program is to broaden the impact of the preservation technology developed for use in the TPAP testbed. To achieve this goal, TPAP team members have participated in multiple meetings on preservation, and have met with many groups that are building preservation environments based on the iRODS data grid. Our intent is to support as broad a range as possible of groups that are pursuing preservation technology. Recent presentations given about the TPAP testbed and the use of policy-based data management systems to implement preservation environments are listed below.

1. Moore, R., "Preservation Interoperability Standards", Proceedings 2010 Meeting of ISO/IEC JTC 1 Study Group on DCMP, Shenzhen, China, August 23-26, 2010.
2. Moore, R., M. Conway, A. Rajasekar, A. de Torcy, "TPAP Preservation Environment", presentations to Society of American Archivists, Washington D. C., August 11, 2010.
3. Moore, R., M. Conway, "Policy-Based Preservation Environments – iRODS," NARA-I, Washington, D.C., August 11, 2010.
4. Moore, R., "Policy-Based Preservation Environment," Society of American Archivists Research Forum, Washington, D.C., August 10, 2010.
5. Moore R., and A. Rajasekar, "iRODS: Data Sharing Technology integrating Communities of Practice", IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society, July 25-30, 2010.
6. Rajasekar A, R. Moore, M. Wan and W. Schroeder, "Cyber Infrastructure for Community Remote Sensing", IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society, July 25-30, 2010.

7. Moore, R., A. Rajasekar, M. Wan, “Policy-based Data Management,” IEEE Policy 2010 workshop, George Mason University, July 21, 2010.
8. Moore, R., A. Rajasekar, M. Wan, W. Schroeder, C-Y Hou, “Policy-based Data Management”, DOE SciDAC Conference, Chattanooga, Tennessee, July 12, 2010.
9. Crabtree, J., “Automated DDI Metadata Harvesting and Replication for Preservation Purposes within iRODS”, IASSIST 2010, New York, June 4, 2010.

The presentations given at NARA are available through a playlist for the National Archives Center for Advanced Systems and Technologies (NCAST) on the usnationalarchives's Channel on YouTube. The playlist is called NCAST Research Presentations and is located at

<http://www.youtube.com/user/usnationalarchives#grid/user/78FCF75A80CF4984>

The first video available through the playlist is

“ Policy Based Preservation Environments (iRODS)”

Wednesday, August 13, National Archives in Washington, DC -- This presentation features Reagan Moore, Mike Conway, and Arcot Rajasekar, NCAST Research Partners from the Data Intensive Cyber Environments (DICE) Group at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, the Renaissance Computing Institute and the Institute for Neural Computation at the University of California, San Diego. Dr. Moore demonstrates several prototype tools that use the integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS) for linking and implementing a repository's preservation policies with record series and collections. For more information, visit the NCAST web site at www.archives.gov/ncast, or visit the iRODS wiki at www.irods.org.

8. Conclusion

The Transcontinental Persistent Archive Prototype has transitioned through many of the technology evolutions expected in preservation environments. The original TPAP testbed was based on the Storage Resource Broker data grid, which focused on strong consistency guarantees for the management of distributed data. The second generation TPAP testbed was based on the iRODS data grid, which enabled evolution of preservation policies through mapping of policies to computer actionable rules. With the present TPAP technology, it is possible to implement a preservation environment that is capable of enforcing preservation policies, automating administrative functions, and validating trustworthiness assessment criteria. Demonstrating these capabilities at the scale of a billion records will not only validate the architecture design, but also ensure that NARA has a viable testbed for managing the expected future preservation archives.

9. Acknowledgement

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Appendix 1: Preservation Tasks for Trustworthiness

	Criteria
1	Address liability and challenges to ownership/rights.
2	Identify the content information and the information properties that the repository will preserve.
3	Maintain a record of the Content Information and the Information Properties that it will preserve.
4	Specify Submission Information Package format (SIP)
5	Verify the depositor of all materials.
6	Verify each SIP for completeness and correctness
7	Maintain the chain of custody during preservation.
8	Document the ingestion process and report to the producer
9	Document administration processes that are relevant to content acquisition.
10	Specify Archival Information Package format (AIP)
11	Label the types of AIPs.
12	Specify how AIPs are constructed from SIPs.
13	Document the final disposition of all SIPs
14	Generate persistent, unique identifiers for all AIPs.
15	Verify uniqueness of identifiers.
16	Manage mapping from unique identifier to physical storage location.
17	Provide authoritative representation information for all digital objects.
18	Identify the file type of all submitted Data Objects.
19	Document processes for acquiring preservation description information (PDI)
20	Execute the documented processes for acquiring PDI.
21	Ensure link between the PDI and relevant Content Information.
22	Verify completeness and correctness of each AIP.
23	Verify the integrity of the repository collections/content.
24	Record actions and administration processes that are relevant to AIP creation.
25	Specify storage of AIPs down to the bit level.
26	Preserve the Content Information of AIPs.
27	Actively monitor the integrity of AIPs.
28	Record actions and administration processes that are relevant to AIP storage.
29	Prove compliance of operations on AIPs to submission agreement.
30	Specify minimum descriptive information requirements to enable discovery.
31	Generate minimum descriptive metadata and associate with the AIP.
32	Maintain link between each AIP and its descriptive information.
33	Enforce access policies.
34	Log and review all access failures and anomalies.
35	Disseminate authentic copies of records
36	Maintain replicas of all records, both content and representation information
37	Detect bit corruption or loss.
38	Report all incidents of data corruption or loss and repair/replace lost data
39	Manage migration to new hardware and media
40	Document processes that enforce management policies
41	Document changes to policies and processes
42	Test and evaluate the effect of changes to the repository's critical processes.
43	Synchronize replicas
44	Delineate roles, responsibilities, and authorization for archivist initiated changes
45	Maintain an off-site backup of all preserved information
46	Maintain access to the requisite Representation Information.
47	Maintain and correct problem reports about errors in data or responses from users.
48	Provide a search interface

49	Perform virus checks
50	Implement a staging area
51	Migrate records to new formats
52	Create and certify Dissemination Information Packages

Appendix 2: Policy Enforcement Points

Policy
Set policy for host access control
Create a new collection with name "childColl" under the parent collection "parColl"
Create default collections (home,trash)
Create a new user
Create collections in Data Grid zone
Pre-process for file delete
Delete the child collection "childColl" under the parent collection "parColl"
Delete home collection
Delete user
Delete collections in a Data Grid zone
Apply the "action" to the list of files that meet the specified condition
Set policy for checking permissions on registering a file
Post-process for collection create
Apply processing to file on copy
Post-process on file create
Post-process on resource creation
Post-process on token creation
Post-process for user create
Post-process for file delete
Post-process on resource deletion
Post-process on token deletion
Post-process for user delete
Post-process for modification of ACLs on data or collection
Post-process for modification of AVU metadata for data/collection/resource/user
Post-process on modification of collection metadata
Post-process on modification of data metadata
Post-process on resource modification
Post-process on resource group modification
Post-process for user modify
Post-process for user group modify
Post-process for object move
Post-process for file read or file read.
Apply processing to file on put
Post-process for collection delete
Pre-process for collection create
Pre-process for resource creation
Pre-process on token creation
Pre-process for user create
Pre-process for file open or read
Pre-process on resource deletion
Pre-process on token deletion
Pre-process for user delete
Pre-process for modification of ACLs on data or collection
Pre-process for modification of AVU metadata for data/collection/resource/user

Pre-process on modification of collection metadata
Pre-process on modification of data metadata
Pre-process on resource modification
Pre-process on resource group modification
Pre-process for user modify
Pre-process for user Group modify
Pre-process for moving a file
Pre-process for collection delete
Purge files satisfying condition on expiration time
Rename the Data Grid zone from the name “oldZone” to the name “newZone”
Specify number of copies per resource
Set the default number of threads for data transfers
Set policy for allowed operations by public
Pre-process on file create, define selection scheme for default resource
Set policy for assigning physical path name
Set policy for using trash can
Optimize the Postgresql database after waiting “arg1” specified time. See delayExec Micro-service

Appendix 3: Micro-Services

Add Rules, state information mapping and function mapping tables to the Rule engine.
Pre-pend another rule file to the core rule file
Change the core rule file
Clear Rules, state information mapping and function mapping tables that were added to the Rule engine.
Display the currently loaded state variable name mappings
Display the currently loaded function name mappings
Display the currently loaded Rules
Apply all applicable Rules when executing a given Rule
Assign a value to a parameter
Break out of While, for and forEach loops
Do not retry any other applicable Rules for this action
Delay execution of micro-Services or Rules
Fail immediately, but recovery and retries are possible
Iterate over a row of tables or a list in a For loop
Execute for loop with initial step and end condition
If-then-else conditional branch
Fail with no recovery.
Sleep
No action
Remote execution of micro-Services or Rules
Succeed immediately
While loop
Write a line (with end of line) to stdout buffer
Write a string to stdout buffer
Close an opened data object
Create a data object
Lseek to a location in a file
Open a data object
Read an opened data object
Write
Check whether user is owner
Check whether permission is granted

Checksum a data object
Copy a file
Get a file (retrieve data from the collection)
Move a data object from one resource to another
Put a file into the collection
Put with additional options
Rename a data object
Replicate a file
Rsync a data between iRODS and local file
Trim the number of replicas
Delete a file
Return type of object: data, collection, resource
Stat an object
Register a physical file into iRODS
Create a collection
Replicate all files in a collection
Delete a collection
Remotely execute a command
Return conversion rate for currencies from one country to another, using web service provided by http://www.webserviceX.NET
Return a stock quotation using web service provided by http://www.webserviceX.NET
Return host name and details given an IP address, using the web service provided by http://ws.fraudlabs.com/
Return position and type of an astronomical object given a name using the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (NED) web service at http://voservices.net/ws_v2_0/NED.asmx
Return an image buffer given a position and cutout size using the SDSS Image Cut Out web service at http://skyserver.sdss.org
Periodically vacuum a Postgres database
Add a user to a group
Commit the database transaction
Create a collection by administrator
Create a new user
Delete a collection by administrator
Delete a user
Execute a given general query structure and return results
Given a condition string create a query, execute it and return the values
Continue an unfinished query
Both make and execute a query
Given a select list and a condition list, creates a pseudo-SQL query
Rename a collection
Rename the local data grid zone
Roll back the database transaction
Commit Changes to the database.
Perform a SQL operation on a remote database but without returning resulting output.
Rollback (don't commit) changes to the database.
Store results in an iRODS DataObject
Access a remote database returning results in standardout.
Create an Xmsg packet, given required information
Receive an Xmsg packet
Send an Xmsg packet
Create a new Message Stream
Connect to the XMessage Server designated by an iRODS Environment file variable
Disconnect from the Xmessage Server
Send email!
Send stdout as email

Ingest object metadata from a AVU structure
Given a key and a keyValPair structure, extract the corresponding value
Print keyvalue pairs to stdout buffer
Remove object metadata using a AVU structure
Convert an array of strings to a string separated by %- signs
Convert %-separated keyvalue pair strings into keyValPair structure
Write keyword value pairs to stdout or stderr, using a specified separator
Add Dublin Core metadata fields to an object or collection
Extract NARA-style metadata from AVU triplets
Extract AVU information using a template
Free a memory buffer
Return the difference between two system time stamps, given in Unix format (stored in a string)
Return the system time for the metadata catalog
Return the local system time of an iRODS Server
Given a TagName get the value from a file in taggedformat (pseudoXML)
Convert a human readable date to a system timestamp
Load AVU metadata from a file
Load template file contents into Tag structure
Write a buffer to stdout or stderr
Write an integer to stdout or stderr
Set the access control policy.
Checksum a data object.
Set the policy for determining certain data cannot be deleted.
Do Not Check file path permission when registering
Set the policy to No trash can.
Specify the Copy to avoid
If the data has multiple copies, specify the preferred Copy to use
Get data type based on file name extension
Set the default storage resource
Set the scheme for composing the physical path in the vault to GRAFT_PATH.
Set the number of copies per resource to unlimited
Set a list of resources that cannot be used by a normal user directly.
Specify the parameters for determining the number of threads to use for data transfer.
Set a list of operations that can be performed by the user "public".
Set the scheme for composing the physical path in the vault to RANDOM.
Set the scheme for selecting the best resource to use
Set the resource from default
Sort the replica randomly when choosing which Copy to use
Stage the data object to the specified resource before operation.
Replicate a data object.
Copy metadata triplets from one object to another object
Create new user from information in a data object
Delete user based on information in a data object
Export metadata AVU triplets for a collection and its contents in a “ ”separated format
Retrieve Audit Trail information for a given action ID
Retrieve Audit Trail information by keywords in the comment field
Retrieve Audit Trail information for an object ID
Retrieve Audit Trail information by time stamp period
Retrieve Audit Trail information for a user ID
Gets ACL (Access Control List) for a collection in ” separated format
Return the object count and total disk usage of a collection
Retrieve metadata AVU triplets for a collection in “ ” separated format
Get ACL (Access Control List) for a data object in “ ” separated format

Get the Archival information Package of a data object in XML format
Retrieves metadata AVU triplets for a data object and return them as an XML file
Retrieve metadata AVU triplets for a data object in “ ” separated format
Get user ACL for all objects and collections
Get information about user
Guess the data type of an object based on its file extension
Load ACL from information in a data object
Parses an object for new metadata AVUs
Modify user information from information in a data object
Recursively copy a collection and its contents including metadata
Set data type for an object
Given an XML object and an XSLT object, return the XML object after applying the XSLT transformation
Read data from an HDF file
Read data attribute from an HDF file
Close an HDF file
Open an HDF file
Read attributes of a group in an HDF file
Add a property and value to a property list. If the property is already in the list, its value is changed. Otherwise the property is added.
Clear a property list
Clone a property list, returning a new property list
Return true (integer 1) if the keyword has a property value in the property list, and false (integer 0) otherwise. The property list is unmodified.
Parse a string into a new property list. The existing property list, if any, is deleted
Get the value of a property in a property list. The property list is left unmodified
Create a new empty property list
Remove a property from the list
Set the value of a property in a property list. If the property is already in the list, its value is changed. Otherwise the property is added.
Convert a property list into a string buffer. The property list is left unmodified.
Return the local system time

Appendix 4: Mapping of preservation environment interoperability requirements defined by Ken Thibodeau (NARA) to NARA TPAP

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures
Discovery	Consumer purpose may be served by current as well as preserved assets	DPA's should be discoverable using generalized pathways and tools that operate across cyberspace	Web services interface, dropbox interface
		DPIF should define an interface that facilitates external search tools operating against a variety of interfaces in preservation repository	Query descriptive metadata from Web browser, Unix utility, Cheshire
	Discovery of DPAs may be hindered by changes in terms over time	Discovery tools could suggest terms related to those entered by consumers	Not yet supported (requires ontology and mapping from descriptive attributes)
		DPIF should define implement a standard syntax for expressing precedence – succession relationships, including cardinality and chronology, for faceted search	System metadata for versioning, time stamps, retention period
	Assets identified in search may include objects which either are or appear to be copies or versions of one another	DPIF should provide a standard for associating copies, versions, and derived products	Replicas, versions, soft links to collections
		Repositories should implement DPIF standard for associating copies, versions and derived products located within their collections and in other repositories	Logical organization in sub-collection
		Consumers should implement DPIF standard to associate copies, versions and derived products with source DPAs, submitting or linking this information to the repositories that provided the DPAs	Soft link to collections in a federated data grid, mounted collection URLs pointing to resource: micro-service to send e-mail or twitter post
	Copies or versions of a DPA may be located both within and outside of the DPD	DPIF standard for associating copies, versions and derived products should be consistent with or capable of two way translation to other methods used for this purpose	Micro-service to package records into appropriate container (Bagit, tar)
	Relevant DPAs may be located in several repositories	DPIF should provide basic syntax and terminology for queries and orders for DIPs, allowing specializations appropriate to the types of information and the Designated Communities of each repository	Queue requests for DIPS, Micro-service to create community specific DIP

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures	
	Result set may include information assets derived from DPAs such that some significant portion(s) of the processing needed for the consumer purpose was accomplished in production of the derived asset(s)	The DPIF standard for associating variants of a DPA should readily link to data provenance information for each variant.	Descriptive metadata for each record (data type, provenance)", Extensible metadata.	
	Consumer may not know where the information is held	Possibility of discovering DPAs should not depend on the repository. A standard method to link from information identifying or characterizing a DPA to a repository which can provide access to it should be part of the DPIF	Data grid mapping of logical name space to storage repository name space	
Relevance	For many purposes, information about assets returned by Internet search engines is not sufficient to determine relevance	DPIF should endorse the Descriptive Information model of OAIS and provide guidance on appropriate levels and types of Descriptive Information, beyond the minimum allowed by OAIS, to enable consumers to determine relevance for different purposes.	Requires template to describe required descriptive information, Micro-service to extract metadata based on XML or pattern matching	
	Norms for descriptive information will vary according to several factors; such as, discipline, type of institution (scientific data center, government archives, university library, health care provider), designated community, et al.	DPIF could establish a standard for common descriptive information to be provided about all DPAs.	Dublin core attributes	
		DPIF could provide a service to translate variant descriptive information to a coherent form, without hiding important idiosyncrasies.	XSLT transformation on XML formatted metadata (descriptive metadata and system metadata)	
	Standards for descriptive information will change over time.	DPIF should provide a mapping between data elements in descriptive standards.	XSLT transformation on XML formatted metadata	
Content	Result list DPAs may be in multiple repositories	DPIF should facilitate requesting copies of, or access to, DPAs that appear on a results list but are preserved in different repositories	Data grid supports access to multiple storage systems; Mounted collection interface.	
	Data Type	Inconsistent or inadequate characterization of data type	DPIF should implement a taxonomy of data types	Data Type system attribute
			Repositories should implement DPIF data type taxonomy	Extensible tokens to define new data types
		DPIF data type taxonomy should be consistent with similar structures used outside the DPD	Remote execution micro-service for executing Pronom, JHOVE services	

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures
Appropriateness	Consumer needs to make an initial assessment of whether the DPA will serve the intended purpose	DPIF should endorse the Preservation Description Information (PDI) model of OAIS and require that sufficient PDI be accessible, independently of a DIP, to enable consumers to assess appropriateness of DPAs	Query across all collection metadata
Adequacy	Consumer purpose may require aggregating data from different sources to provide consistent coverage over a length of time.	Utility to display chronological coverage of an arbitrary set of assets on a time line	Query on time stamps
		Ability to create, maintain, and modify a virtual collection, drawn from several repositories, organized according to temporal coverage. Possibility for other users to discover and use such virtual collections.	Logical organization of a sub-collection; Use of soft links to create sub-collection
	Possibility of using a DPA of a given data type may depend on availability of information in another data type; e.g., encoded data requires codebooks for interpretation; textual documents may require external font libraries; etc.	Standards for preserving relationships among DPAs	Either organize in collections, or assign descriptive metadata
Precision	Syntax and semantics for specifying precision may vary	Repositories should implement standard methods for specifying precision appropriate to a given discipline or content domain	Descriptive metadata about precision for each record
		DPIF should include an abstract grammar for specifying precision suitable for tracking changes in lower level specifications in given domains over time.	Workflow that applies math functions to process descriptive metadata: Example is deadline scheduler
Reliability	Reliability may vary substantially across a set of information assets derived from multiple sources	DPIF should provide a common syntax and semantics for repositories to communicate with producers and consumers about reliability	Audit trails for events: Micro-services to parse audit trails and generate summary statistics
	Different purposes may entail different ways of determining reliability	DPIF should facilitate the use of standard, discipline-specific approaches to determining reliability for different purposes and different data types	Parsing of audit trails by data type, storage system; Verification of checksums.
		DPIF should provide or utilize a meta-semantics for characterizing different approaches to determining reliability.	Creation of separate policies for evaluating reliability
Accuracy	DPAs with related content may have different		Descriptive metadata on accuracy of

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures
	levels of accuracy		each record
Producer	Promising DPAs may come from several producers	DPIF could provide standards for metadata about producers	Descriptive metadata about producer of DPA
Data Provenance	The chain of preservation or other preservation data may not adequately or accurately identify producers or processes that brought the data to its preserved state.	DPIF should include minimum standards for data provenance for different data types Beyond the minimum, DPIF should facilitate preservation and communication of data provenance metadata as specified in standards applicable to different disciplines	Requires template defining required provenance for each data type: Requires template defining DIP for packaging provenance metadata.
Preservation	Information could be corrupted over time.	DPIF should provide standards for describing how DPAs have been preserved MOIMS-RAC supplement to OAIS standard will provide basis for assessing the trustworthiness of a repository	Track policy version for replication, integrity checking, chain of custody Implement the 52 computer-actionable criteria derived from ISO MOIMS-rac
	Information about RAC certification of trustworthy repositories may not be readily available		Manage reports on each collection for the 54 management sustainability criteria
	There are likely to be variations in repository certification information both between different repositories and over time.		Track versions of certification reports.
	Certification of trustworthiness of a repository may not be sufficient to determine that a DPA in that repository has been appropriately preserved.	Repositories should provide preservation information about DPAs	Parse audit trails to track operations on records; Verify checksum; Compare record series members to submission template.
Interpretation	Various factors, such as differences in the ways data was created or collected, variations in the performance of instruments, et al., can be important for valid interpretation of data	Repositories should identify the types of factors which can influence interpretation of data within the scope of their collections and motivate producers to report accordingly.	Context managed for each record as descriptive metadata, or context associated via an XML file; or associated properties file
		DPIF should define standard tags for indicating the presence of idiosyncratic factors impacting on interpretation.	Descriptive metadata defined for a collection; Micro-services that implement multiple versions of

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures
		DPIF should provide guidance on how to indicate interpretive considerations in PDI and Representation Information.	parsing functions;
Usefulness			
Acquiring or accessing	Are there restrictions on release, use, or downstream dissemination, including derived products	Standard formulation of restrictions that is invariant regardless of producer or repository	Roles; ACLs on Roles; Constraints on access policies;
Acquiring	Does the volume of an asset impede physical transfer?	Repositories should facilitate access to and processing of data within the repository when data volume or other factors make transfer difficult	Execution of remote micro-services; Deadline scheduler for manipulation of entire archives.
	Does the volume of a set of assets impede physical transfer?		
	Packaging of DPAs in AIPs or DIPs may be ill suited to a consumer's needs	DPIF should provide guidance on approaches to packaging DPAs that facilitate discretionary selections and joins	Micro-services that generate preferred container; Template-based specification for DIP
Accessing	Can an asset be accessed and desired processing performed within the repository?	DPIF should provide standard syntax and semantics for identifying constraints.	Virtual execution of workflows; Tracking of all policies that apply for access operation.
	DPAs that cannot easily be transferred may be in different repositories with different possibilities for access and in situ processing		Integration with external workflow systems through explicit staging of data; Compound resources for accessing cloud storage:
Format	Does the repository have a coherent approach for identifying formats from different generations of technology?	DPIF should have a common and comprehensive taxonomy of data formats	Query on data type.
		DPIF data format taxonomy should include current as well as obsolete formats. Entries for current formats should be unambiguously linkable to corresponding metadata used to identify and characterize the same formats outside of the DPD	Policy that periodically assesses types of data present in collection; Policies that query external resource to extract information. Ability to execute web service as a micro-service.
	Does the repository have a coherent approach for identifying formats when the relevant assets came from multiple producers?	DPIF data format taxonomy should provide for local extensions	Attributes specific to a record.
		DPIF taxonomy should have a service for identifying duplicate or similar format captured as	Micro-service that compares lists of types of data formats. The list can be

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures	
		local extensions	stored as a collection property.	
		DPIF taxonomy should facilitate elevation of duplicate local extension to DPD level	Policy on collections to generate aggregate list of duplicate extensions	
		Different repositories may use different ways to identify and characterize digital formats.	DPIF should define or adopt a metadata standard for exchange and dissemination of information about digital formats	Invocation of JHOVE, or PRONOM as a micro-service
		Various disciplines and communities of consumers may have different needs for information about formats		Policy for summarizing format information across collection
Processing	Can tools for performing desired processing be applied to the target DPAs?	DPIF ontology should provide for specifying the domain of format(s) that can be input or output of a tool.	Micro-services (media adaptors) for transformative migration: Micro-services for domain specific data manipulation (HDF5): Invocation of Peter Bajcsy transformation mechanisms as a micro-service	
		DPIF Ontology should include a taxonomy of processing services including transformation, data interlinking, integration, fusion, analysis, annotation, presentation, and others		
		DPIF taxonomy of processing services should identify which services can be applied to common formats of DPAs without transformation.		
		The DPIF taxonomy of services should be consistent with related taxonomies in wide use in cyberspace		
	Consumer requirements may entail use of distributed capabilities such as computational grids, data grids, et al.	The DPIF should include standard service interfaces that enable use of distributed external resources for processing of DPAs	Integration of workflow server with data servers to use external resources to process DPAs	
		DPIF should specify standard interfaces for OAIS compliant repositories to connect to grid resources	Interoperation with grid through workflow server	
	Processing of sets of DPAs may require special capabilities for temporal interlinking, integration or fusion	DPIF should specify standard translation of different chronological and temporal scales	Integration with HDF5: Require integration with NetCDF; Micro-services to perform time-series integration: Micro-services to parse time formats:	
		DPIF should define common services for temporal integration or fusion		
		DPIF should define standard service interfaces for mediation services for resolving semantic and syntactic inconsistencies specifically related to the temporal dimension		

Requirement	Challenge	How Interoperability Could Help	TPAP Preservation Procedures
		DPIF should specify interface for invoking semantic and syntactic mediation services available in cyberspace	Micro-services for invoking external web services.
	If selected processing cannot be performed on DPAs in the formats in which they are preserved, can the DPAs easily be transformed to suitable formats?	DPIF ontology should include identification of feasible transformations with characterization of data loss or other changes entailed by each transformations	Integration with Peter Bajcsy transformation service as micro-service
	Tools may not be able to process all the formats in which similar content exists	DPIF should facilitate the creation, continuing enrichment, and sharing of registries of metadata about the suitability of tools useful for processing DPAs	Chaining of micro-services into a procedure, and registration as a policy;
	If the assets are located in multiple repositories and some must be processed in their current locations, can desired processing be performed consistently on all target assets?		Distribution of workflows across multiple storage locations.
Combination	Consumer may need to create data integration, fusion, or other combinations of information of a variety of both preserved and current information assets	DPIF should facilitate discovery, by repositories or consumers, and determination of appropriateness of services for various combinations of data including multiple instances of data of a single data type or format and of heterogeneous data types and formats.	Policies for explicitly characterizing data integration requests.
		DPIF should facilitate sharing of information about data combination services and their performances, especially with respect to data types and formats that are more frequent or important in the DPD than in cyberspace generally	Publication of Policies.